

**CHEMICAL USED IN THE TREATMENT OF DISEASES OF
THE ORAL CAVITY**

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the types, classification and causes of oral diseases. The chemical composition of some drugs used in the treatment of these diseases is also given.

The oral cavity is the main entrance to our internal organs in the human body, especially the digestive system. Therefore, it provides information about all changes in the oral cavity, various changes or diseases of the internal organs.

Below we provide information about the causes of oral diseases, types of diseases and methods of their treatment.

Any disease does not appear by chance, but can be caused by our lifestyle, malnutrition, lack of certain substances in the body, nervous tension and many other reasons.

The mucous membrane of the oral cavity is completely different from the mucous membrane of other organs. It can

show the condition of the whole body and organs. The mucous membrane of the oral cavity is always under the influence of external factors. Its changes occur in the body with cardiovascular diseases, metabolic diseases, skin and genital diseases, infectious and gastrointestinal diseases. It is important to be able to correctly determine the causes of the disease and the localization of pathological changes in the diagnosis of diseases of the oral mucosa.

Currently, the following factors can cause diseases of the oral mucosa, lips and tongue (Table 1).

Table 1
Factors that cause diseases of the lips and tongue

Type of disease	Pathogens
Lip and tongue	Injuries caused by various injuries
Lip and tongue	Complications of infectious diseases
Lip and tongue	Inflammation after complications of allergic diseases
Lip and tongue	As a result of smoking and drinking alcohol
Lip and tongue	Vitamin deficiency

Lip and tongue	Disruption of endocrine glands
Lip and tongue	Inflammation caused by infections as a result of non-compliance with oral hygiene
Lip and tongue	Installation of poor-quality dental prostheses
Lip and tongue	Decreased body immunity
Lip and tongue	Extremely hot or cold, spicy or sweet, sour or salty foods

Below are some inflammatory diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity let's stop: Stomatitis is one of the most frequently observed diseases of the oral cavity, and it is also called an inflammatory disease of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, i.e. oral thrush.

Despite the fact that the form of this disease is different, they have a common sign. That is, in this disease, the mucous membrane of the oral cavity becomes red. The tissues around it swell, the lymph nodes under the jaw enlarge. The disease is acute and chronic.

Gingivitis is inflammation of the gums. It develops under the influence of local and general factors and passes without damage to the tooth-gum connection. This disease was observed not only in middle-aged and elderly patients, but also in 80 percent of young children. Lack of vitamins A, B, C, E affects the development of gingivitis. Catarrhal gingivitis, ulcerative gingivitis, stomatitis can also be observed in case of poisoning from metals such as lead, mercury, iodine, zinc and aluminum.

Changes in gastrointestinal activity often cause pathological changes in the language. As a result of such changes, the appearance of the tongue changes and becomes "black-haired" or rhombus. This is a disease related to the tongue, called glossitis. The epithelium of the tongue manifests itself in

diseases of the gastrointestinal tract and liver due to a violation of the diet, metabolic disorders, drinking alcohol, smoking, taking various antibiotics for a long time. If the defects that caused the disease are eliminated, the patient gradually recovers.

In addition to changes in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, gums and tongue, there are also diseases of the lips. Inflammatory disease of the red border of the lip is called kiyat; There are types such as angular, granular and exfoliative.

Angular arthritis is a type of chronic relapsing disease caused by fungi and infections. Pain occurs when the patient opens his mouth. Inflammatory sores appear in the corners of the mouth.

Granular goitre is an inflammation of small salivary glands. It is possible to observe the enlargement of the salivary glands as red dots in the transition area of the normal granular mass to the red border of the lip, and the secretion of drops of saliva.

5-10 seconds after drying the lips, separated drops of saliva cover the entire lip. In some cases, circular leukoplakia can be formed on the salivary duct.

Exfoliative psoriatic arthritis is a chronic disease that occurs only with damage to the lips. Oral diseases and synthetic drugs used in their treatment and their chemical composition are listed in Table 2 below.

Table 2

Oral diseases and synthetic drugs used in their treatment and their chemical composition

№	<i>Types of diseases.</i>	<i>Chemical composition.</i>	<i>Name and classification used</i>
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1	Stomatitis	Active substance - hexetidine 1.00 mg (C ₂₁ H ₄₅ N ₃), auxiliary components: propyl glycol, polysorbate-20, sodium saccharinate, racementol, methyl salicylate.	Stomatidine. Inflammation of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. Unbiased. Active substance - choline salicylate; C ₁₂ H ₁₉ NO ₄ . Excipients: hydroxyethyl cellulose, glycerin, methylparahydroxybenzoate, propolparahydroxybenzoate, purified water. Candide. Active substance: clotrimazole C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ . Excipients: propylglycol, carbomer-940, levomenthol, sodium hydroxide.
2	Gingivitis	The active ingredient is metronidazole benzoate equivalent to metronidazole - 10 mg. C ₆ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	Milkningyallig'lanishi. Anasep Gel. Yordamchimoddalar: xlorgeksidinglyukonat, karbomer, propilenglikol, glitserin. Metrogildenta. Faolmoddalar: metronidazole benzoate, 16 mg xlorgeksidinbiglyukonat C ₂₂ H ₃₂ Cl ₂ N ₁₀ Yordamchimoddalar: propilenglikol, karbomer-940, disodiyedetat, natriysaharinat, levomentol, natriygidroksid.
3	Glossitis	Active substance: nystatin - 500 000IU; C ₄₇ H ₇₅ NO ₁₇ Excipients: sugar, calcium stearate, talc, potato starch, methylcellulose, E-104, orange E-110.	Inflammation of the mucous membrane of the tongue. The appearance of fissures on the tongue. Kamistad gel.
4	Cheilite	Active substance: fluconazole 150 mg, (2,4-difluorophenyl)-1,3-bis(1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)-2-propanol. C ₁₃ H ₁₂ F ₂ N ₆ O Excipients: gietellose-20.0 mg, methyl parahydroxybenzoate-1.5 mg, propyl parahydroxybenzoate-0.8 mg, glycerin-50.0 mg, anise seed oil-1.61 mg, ethanol 96%-390 ,0 mg, water-up to 10 ng.	Inflammation of the red border of the lip. Fluconazole. Unbiased.
5	Periodontitis	Active substance: furatsillin-20.0 mg; C ₆ H ₆ N ₄ O ₃ . Excipients: sodium chloride-	Inflammation of subdental tissue, gums. Furacillin. Manganese.

800.0 mg

In conclusion, we can say that due to the additional negative effects of any chemical preparations, it would be appropriate to improve the methods of using folk medicine in the treatment of oral cavity diseases. Many of the following have been used in the treatment of these diseases

since ancient times: carrots, chamomile, garlic, sorghum, oak bark, cloves, mint, etc. plants are used. In order to develop optimal methods of using these plants, the composition of some chemical drugs used in the treatment of oral cavity diseases was studied.

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